

Supporting Information

ZnGa₂O₄ polycrystalline thin-film preparation using hydrothermally synthesized nanoparticles

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Figure S1 Determination of E_g in the Tauc plots and obtained E_g of the ZGO thin films annealed at (a) 500 °C, (b) 600 °C, (c) 700 °C, and (d) 800 °C and the (e) hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles.